

Towards Treatment Patterns Validation in Lung Cancer Patients

Abstract—Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer death. From the estimation of cases that will be in 2021, more than 230,000 new cases are expected to be of lung cancer patients, with an estimation of more than 131,000 deaths. Improving the survival rates or the patient's quality of life is partially covered by a common element: treatments. Collective knowledge about cancer treatment recommendations is typically included in *clinical guidelines*, intended to optimize patient care and assist clinicians in lung cancer treatment. These guidelines define a set of treatment paths, where recommendations depend on cancer disease aspects and individual features for a concrete patient.

Although oncologists are expected to follow clinical guidelines, the inter and intrapatient's variability of response to the possible treatment combinations, makes it necessary to personalize different treatment-patterns on certain cases. Additionally, clinical guidelines are not frequently updated with new findings or lack a consistent methodology when they are frequently updated. For that reason, the analysis of patterns on both patients treated following the standard of care, or outside it, would allow to validate clinical guidelines and identify potential new treatment recommendations. In this work, we have analysed whether actual treatments prescribed to lung cancer patients follow clinical guidelines or not. Using a machine learning method that provides as output association rules (Apriori), we identify patterns based on cancer stage. These preliminary results show that treatments patterns found mostly match with clinical guidelines recommendations, validating the information included in the consulted guidelines.

Index Terms—lung cancer, machine learning, apriori analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer ranks as a leading cause of death and an important barrier to increasing life expectancy worldwide. The burden of cancer incidence not only represents a matter of global health, but also has an enormous impact in economy and healthcare systems feasibility. According to Eurostat [1], in 2016, 1.2 million people died from cancer in the EU-27, which represented more than one quarter (25.8%) of the total number of deaths. The last statistics from the American Cancer Society (ACS) [2] estimates that in 2021 will be approximately 1,898,160 new cancer cases and 608,570 cancer deaths in the United States. The more recent statistics and estimations from the ACS shown a reduction in the death rate from its peak in 1991 through 2018, for a total decline of 31% due to the reductions in smoking and the improvement in early detection and treatments.

Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer death. From the estimation of cases that will be in 2021, more than 230,000 new cases are expected to be of lung cancer patients, with an estimation of more than 131,000 deaths.

Although in the last decade survival of lung cancer patients has significantly increased (specifically in non-small lung cancer patients - "NSCLC 2-year relative survival increased from 34% for persons diagnosed during 2009 through 2010 to 42% during 2015 through 2016" [2]), greater efforts to improve screening methods and treatments are still needed in order to improve patient's survival and quality of life.

Improving the survival rates or the patient's quality of life is partially covered by a common element: treatments. Although any drug is susceptible of provoking secondary effects, cancer treatments are well known for the toxic outcomes and secondary effects on the patients. These toxicities can seriously alter the homeostatic equilibrium of the body, causing different health problems that impact the patient's quality of life. Reducing toxicities without a decline on the positive survival effect is an important goal that aims to be pursued from the clinical perspective. One of the potential approaches that are under study are those referred to patient's similar profiles [3]–[5], and how these similarities (or dissimilarities) can affect the treatment outcomes. This approach, which is part of the so-called "Precision Medicine" allows to make use of computational and data-driven approaches to find potential solutions to different health problems. In the context of this domain, we aim at finding patterns of the patient characteristics that allows to identify better outcomes in terms of the survival or in the reduction of the toxicities. Although oncologists are expected to follow clinical guidelines [6], [7], the inter and intrapatient's variability of response to the possible treatment combinations, makes it necessary to personalize different treatment-patterns on certain cases. The identification of patterns on both the patients that have been treated following the standard of care, or outside it, would allow to identify potential treatment recommendations based on the patient characteristics.

In this work, we have analysed the outcome of treatments on lung cancer patients following clinical guidelines or not. For this task, we have used a machine learning method that provides as output association rules (Apriori). By using as first input characteristic the patient stage, we can identify potential patterns that match with the clinical guidelines, and others that are outside them. The clinical information about the patients was provided by Hospital Universitario Puerta de Hierro- Majadahonda and it is the result of previous work extracting clinical information from electronic health records [8], [9].

II. RELATED WORK

Machine Learning (ML) in the area of Lung Cancer has been used in recent years showing promising results. Beyond the analysis of data coming from radiological and imaging diagnostic procedures, machine learning has been widely used for patient survival estimation. A recent work used ML algorithms to accurately classify multi-category survival-outcome of lung adenocarcinoma. Combining clinical data, transcriptomic data and clinico-transcriptomic and using three ML models, authors were able to estimate treatment survival-outcome and identify sets of genes associated to treatments outcomes [10].

Related with diagnosis and prognosis, recent works [11]–[13] performed patient and tumor profiling based on different histopathology related markers. Based on these markers, classifiers have been used with different purposes like cancer diagnose, cancer type/subtype identification and specific therapy discovery.

All these advances are typically reflected on clinical practice guidelines. Clinical guidelines include recommendations intended to optimize patient care and therefore guidelines are essential to assist clinicians in lung cancer treatment. However, a previous work [14] analyzing guidelines from different cancer associations, concluded that either these guidelines are not frequently updated with new findings or lack a consistent methodology when they are frequently updated. Thus, in this work we study the adoption of clinical guidelines [6], [7], [15]–[20] when compared with treatments prescribed to lung cancer patients.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section presents data acquisition and preprocessing steps together with a description of the selected variables. Also, the clinical guidelines against which we compare our results are summarized. Finally, we provide a brief description of the machine learning methods.

A. Data acquisition and preprocessing

In this study we consider a dataset composed of structured information about 1242 patients, provided by the Medical Oncology Department at Puerta de Hierro University Hospital (HUPHM). It contains information coming from the Electronic Health Records (EHRs), which describe all phases of the diagnosis and treatment, as well as personal and medical data recorded during anamneses. Data was structured in the following categories and subcategories:

- Patient information: demographic information, smoking habit, medical history (including comorbidities and previous cancers information of the patient and his/her relatives) and diagnosis (including diagnosis date, symptomatology, histology, molecular markers, cancer initial stage, primary tumor size, tnm stadification, metastatic locations and previous treatments).
- Treatments: chemotherapy, radiotherapy and surgery. For each treatment, the dataset contains information about the purpose, the specific type of treatment, the number of

therapies received and the immediate effect on the patient (response and associated toxicities developed). Duration and treatment dates as well as other specific characteristics were also included. Chemotherapy subcategory also includes other types of therapies such as immunotherapy and targeted oral therapy.

- Cancer Evolution: cancer relapses (including types, dates and location(s)) and current situation of the patients with respect to the cancer (death, alive without cancer or alive with persistent cancer). In the case of dead patients, the date and cause is also registered.

During the initial exploratory analysis we detected some missing values and data inconsistencies. Since temporality is a key factor in our analysis, we cleaned data focusing on treatment and diagnostic dates. Particularly, we checked that a patient's treatments have associated the corresponding dates, or at least the starting date, as well as the coherency of dates (i.e. starting date must be previous to end date, and diagnostic date must be previous to treatment date). Also, patients who did not received any treatment were discarded. After the cleaning process the number of patients was reduced from 1242 to 1074.

B. Data description

As mentioned above, our goal is to characterize lung cancer patients, focussing on the initial stage of their tumors and the first treatment they received. Accordingly, a subset of variables was selected from the original dataset, which are described below.

Cancer initial stage was selected from patient information. This variable contains information about the cancer stages according to the TNM estadificacion system of the American Joint Committee on Cancer [21]. TNM estadificacion system updated from version 7 [22] to version 8 [21] in January 2017, but the dataset includes formerly diagnosed patients. Thus, data referst to the stages stablished in both versions, which are defined as follows:

- IA: Small tumor (greatest diameter ≤ 3 cm) surrounded by lung or visceral pleura without metastasis.
- IB: Tumor with diameter between 3 and 4 cm without metastasis
- IIA: Tumor with diameter between 4 and 5 cm without metastasis
- IIB: Tumor with diameter between 5 and 7 cm without metastasis or smaller than 5 cm with metastasis in ipsilateral peribronchial and/or hilar lymph nodes.
- IIIA: Tumor with diameter > 7 cm without metastasis or diameter > 5 cm with metastasis in ipsilateral peribronchial and/or hilar lymph nodes or diameter < 5 cm with metastasis in ipsilateral mediastinal and/or subcarinal lymph nodes.
- IIIB: Tumor with diameter > 5 cm with metastasis in ipsilateral mediastinal and/or subcarinal lymph nodes or diameter < 5 cm with metastasis in supraclavicular lymph nodes, ipsilateral or contralateral scalene, contralateral mediastinal or contralateral hilar.

Fig. 1. Number of patients according to the initial cancer stage.

- IIC: Tumor with diameter > 5 cm with metastasis in supraclavicular lymph nodes, ipsilateral or contralateral scalene, contralateral mediastinal or contralateral hilar.
- IV: Tumor of any size with distant metastasis.
- IVA: Tumor of any size with distant metastasis in a single organ or with separate tumour nodules in contralateral lobe.
- IVB: Tumor of any size with multiple distant extrathoracic metastases in one or several organs.

Figure 1 shows the number of patients according to the cancer stage at the initial diagnosis. It can be clearly seen that most of them presents quite advanced stage of disease. More than 22% of patients were diagnosed with a IV stage, and this figure rises to 54% when patients with a IVA and IVB stage are summed up. Even when IIC has a low value (3.3%), stages IIIA and IIB presents the third and fifth highest values (13 and 10.4% respectively). Patients on early stages (IA-B and IIA-B) do not reach a 16% of the total.

Regarding the treatments, we observe five different types: chemotherapy (CT), radiotherapy (RT), surgery (SUR), targeted oral therapy (also named as *Drugs*), and immunotherapy (*Imm*), which prevents PD-1 from binding with PD-L1, making the T-lymphocyte able to detect and reduce tumor cells. In the dataset, chemotherapy, targeted oral therapy and immunotherapy were grouped in the same variable: CT. Together with the treatment date, we included information about the purpose and application of the treatment later in the analyses.

As observed in Figure 2, most of the patients (64.5%) received chemotherapy as the first treatment, followed by surgery (21.4%) and radiotherapy (14.1%). Taking into account possible concurrencies, we detected that some of the patients that received chemotherapy as the first treatment, also received a radiotherapy treatment at the same time (4.4% of the total of patients).

According to their intention, we can find the following RT subtypes:

Fig. 2. Number of patients according to the type of the first treatment they received.

- Adjuvant (RT_{Adj}): radiotherapy complementary to other treatments to prevent relapses.
- Neoadjuvant (RT_{NeoAdj}): radiotherapy applied before any local treatment to reduce the tumor size.
- Palliative (RT_{Pallia}): radiotherapy aimed to improve symptoms and prolong survival.
- Prophylactic (RT_{Prophy}): radiotherapy directed at the head to reduce the risk of cancer spreading to the brain.
- Radical ($RT_{Radical}$): single radiotherapy aimed to cure the disease and/or maintain the function of the organ.

Similarly, we can distinguish between these four kind of surgeries:

- Curative (SUR_{Curat}): surgery oriented to remove all malignant tissue.
- Diagnostic (SUR_{Diag}): surgery aimed to confirm a suspicion of the presence of cancer.
- Palliative (SUR_{Pallia}): surgery targeted to reduce symptoms.
- Rebiopsy (SUR_{Rebiop}): surgery oriented to know the nature of new lesions.

Finally, we can divide CT in the following subcategories:

- Immunotherapy (CT_{Imm}).
- Targeted oral therapy (CT_{Drugs}).
- Adjuvant chemotherapy (CT_{Adj}): chemotherapy complementary to other treatments to prevent relapses.
- Neoadjuvant chemotherapy (CT_{NeoAdj}): applied before any local treatment to reduce the tumor size.
- Oral chemotherapy (CT_{Oral}): chemotherapy orally administered.
- Intravenous chemotherapy (CT_{Intrav}): chemotherapy given by an intravenous line.
- Intravenous and oral chemotherapy ($CT_{Intrav\&Oral}$): chemotherapy that can be administered either orally or by an intravenous line.
- Intravenous chemotherapy + immunotherapy ($CT_{Intrav+Immuno}$): intravenous and immunotherapy

Fig. 3. Number of patients according to the specific subtype of the first treatment received.

combination.

- Chemotherapy + concomitant radiotherapy ($CT_{CT-RTConc}$): both treatments are applied simultaneously.
- Chemotherapy + sequential radiotherapy ($CT_{CT-RTSeq}$): one treatment after the other.
- Chemotherapy + adjuvant radiotherapy ($CT_{CT-RTAdj}$): combination of treatments aimed to prevent relapses.
- Chemotherapy + neoadjuvant radiotherapy ($CT_{CT-RTNeoadj}$): combination of treatments aimed to reduce the tumor size.
- Others.

Figure 3 depicts the number of patients according the specific subtype of the first treatment they received.

C. Clinical guidelines

Clinical guidelines include recommendations intended to optimize patient care and therefore guidelines are essential to assist clinicians in lung cancer treatment. These guidelines define a set of treatment paths, where recommendations depend on cancer disease aspects and individual features for a concrete patient. Table I describes the aspects present in the guidelines we have considered [6], [7], [15]–[20].

We have defined a rule representation of clinical guidelines paths in order to ease the comparison with the treatment association rules obtained in this paper. Thus, we propose a representation using the following general notation:

$$\underbrace{STAGE(ASPECT)}_{\text{antecedent}} \rightarrow \underbrace{[TREATMENT LIST]}_{\text{consequent}} \quad (1)$$

The notation in Equation 1 states that the list of treatments in the consequent is advised when the antecedent is met, in

TABLE I
ASPECTS CHECKED IN CLINICAL GUIDELINES

Aspect	Description	Answers
Surgery (SUR)	Can surgery be performed?	Yes No
Resectable (RES)	Is the tumor resectable?	Yes No Potentially
Mutations (MUT)	Patient with driver mutations?	Yes No
Oligometastatic (OLIG)	Oligometastatic lung cancer?	Yes No
Metastases (MET)	Brain, bone or spinal metastases?	Yes No
Palliative care (PAL)	Due to disease evolution, palliative care is the only possible treatment?	Yes No

terms of cancer stage and cancer aspects (see Table I). Thus for example, the following rule:

$$I(SUR? : YES) \rightarrow [CT, SUR]$$

Advices that, when tumor is in stage 1 (I) and is possible to perform surgery (SUR? : YES), then apply two treatments, one after another: first apply chemotherapy (CT), then perform surgery (SUR).

On the other hand, clinical guidelines also specify treatments within the different options, that must be applied jointly but in two different ways: concurrently or sequentially. Examples of these treatment applications can be seen in the following stage III rules:

$$III(RES? : NO) \rightarrow [conc(CT + RT), DRUGS]$$

$$III(RES? : NO) \rightarrow [seq(CT + RT)]$$

The first rule advices that, if tumor is in stage III and tumor is not resectable (RES? : NO), apply two treatments, one after another: the first one a concurrent application (conc(...)) of chemotherapy (CT) and radiotherapy (RT), then apply targeted oral therapy (DRUGS). The second rule advices that, if tumor is in stage III and tumor is not resectable, then use one treatment consisting on a sequential application (seq(...)) of chemotherapy (CT) and radiotherapy (RT). Based on this notation, the full set of clinical guidelines paths we have obtained, is listed on the right most column in Table II, group by cancer stage.

D. Machine Learning methods

In order to perform a preliminary analysis of treatment prescriptions included in the dataset, we have used Apriori algorithm [23]. Apriori is a machine learning method typically used for frequent item set mining and association rule learning over relational databases. It proceeds by identifying the frequent individual items in a database and extending them to larger item sets as long as those item sets appear sufficiently often in the database. The frequent item sets determined by

Apriori can be used to obtain association rules which reveal general trends in the database.

Apriori algorithm handles frequency of items based on three concepts: *support*, *confidence* and *lift*. *Support* of a given item is defined as the fraction of database records containing such item. In its turn, *confidence* allows to define relations among items in the database. For a relation ($X \rightarrow Y$) between items X and Y , the *confidence* is the likelihood of finding item Y when item X is found. Finally, *lift* refers to the increase in the ratio of finding an item. Thus, $Lift(X \rightarrow Y)$ provides a measure of how much the ratio of finding Y increases when X is found.

We have performed Apriori analysis in Python using the package `apriori` [24]. This package allows to vary the set of association rules obtained, by specifying minimum threshold values for: *support*, *confidence* and *lift*. Since we want to find frequent and not so frequent treatments prescriptions, we used the following values: `support=0.005`, `lift=0.5`. However, even for rare treatment prescriptions, we want to avoid associations with low confidence, so we set the minimum threshold to 0.2 (i.e. a 20%).

IV. RESULTS

This section describes the results obtained from the application of the Apriori algorithm to the data described in Section III-B. Association rules obtained show the link between patients cancer stage and initial treatments prescribed. Thus, Table II shows the association rules obtained (first column from the left), along with support and confidence values (second and third columns), and the information from clinical guidelines recommendations (forth column), according to notation described in Section III-C. In addition, association rules and clinical guidelines paths in Table II are grouped by cancer stage.

Looking at rules obtained by Apriori analysis (Table II), under stage I rule II.1 states that for stage IA, surgery is prescribed to patients with a support of 4.4% and confidence of 96%. Rule II.2 states that for stage IB, surgery is prescribed to patients with a support of 3.11% and confidence of 85%. Regarding stage I, clinical guidelines recommendations suggest that the application of neoadjuvant CT before surgery is optional depending on tumor characteristics. For that reason, association rules obtained for stage I agree with clinical guidelines recommendations.

For stage II, two association rules are obtained by Apriori analysis (see Table II). Rule II.3 states that for stage IIA, surgery is prescribed to patients with a support of 4.03% and confidence of 73.33%. Rule II.4 states that for stage IIB, surgery is prescribed to patients with a support of 1.47% and confidence of 88.89%. As for stage I, clinical guidelines recommendations for stage II suggest that the application of neoadjuvant CT before surgery is optional depending on tumor characteristics. For that reason, association rules obtained for stage II agree with clinical guidelines recommendations.

For stage III four association rules are obtained by Apriori analysis (see Table II). The first one (rule II.5) states that

for stage IIIA, chemotherapy is prescribed to patients with a support of 8.06% and confidence of 61.97%. Rule II.6 states that for stage IIIB, chemotherapy is prescribed to patients with a support of 7.51% and confidence of 71.93%. Rule II.7 states that for stage IIIA, surgery is prescribed to patients with a support of 3.85% and confidence of 29.58%. Finally, rule II.8 states that for stage IIIC, chemotherapy is prescribed to patients with a support of 3.11% and confidence of 94.44%. When comparing these association rules with clinical guidelines we see a coincidence since CT is advised as a first treatment for stage IIIA, as stated by the following guidelines recommendation:

$$IIIA (RES? : POT) \rightarrow [CT, SUR]$$

And the dataset reveals that more often CT is prescribed as a first treatment (rule II.5). At the same time, surgery is less often applied directly for stage IIIA (rule II.7). This pattern matches with clinical recommendations, since a direct application of surgery is possible depending on tumor's resectability, that is evaluated by the surgical department. The other two rules (i.e. II.6 and II.8) refer to stages IIIB and IIIC and there is no direct reference to such stages in clinical guidelines. Nevertheless, the associated treatment for these stages is chemotherapy, compliant with clinical guidelines. Additionally, the dataset does not contain any treatment containing CT and RT, combined either sequential or concurrently, as stated by clinical guidelines recommendations.

For stage IV six association rules are obtained by Apriori analysis (see Table II). The first one (rule II.9) states that for stage IV, chemotherapy is prescribed, with a support of 18.13% and confidence of 80.49%. Rule II.10 states that for stage IVB, chemotherapy is also prescribed with a support of 10.81% and confidence of 54.63%. Rule II.11 states that for stage IVA, chemotherapy is prescribed with a support of 8.24% and confidence of 70.31%. Rule II.12 states that for stage IVB, radiotherapy is prescribed with a support of 6.59% and confidence of 49.32%. Rule II.13 states that for stage IV, radiotherapy is prescribed with a support of 3.30% and confidence of 24.66%. Finally, rule II.14 states that for stage IVB, a concurrent treatment combining chemotherapy and radiotherapy is prescribed with a support of 1.47% and confidence of 47.06%.

For stage IV, clinical recommendations mostly agree with association rules obtained, since CT and RT are prescribed as a first treatment. On the other hand, clinical guidelines recommendations for stage IV include specific treatments like targeted oral therapy (DRUGS) or immunotherapy (IMM), which are considered as CT treatments subtypes in the dataset (see Section III-B). For that reason, we have obtained a new set of association rules for stage IV in order to account for these treatment subtypes.

The new set of rules for stage IV is shown in Table III. Association rules reveal that similar treatments prescribed for stage IV coincide with respect to clinical guidelines, like: DRUGS (rules III.15 and III.17), $CT_{Intrav.}$ (rules III.3, III.4

TABLE II
ASSOCIATION RULES AND CLINICAL GUIDELINES RECOMMENDATIONS

Stage I				
Rules		Sup.	Conf.	Clinical guidelines
II.1	IA → [SUR]	4.40 %	96.00 %	I (SUR? : YES) → [CT, SUR]
II.2	IB → [SUR]	3.11 %	85.00 %	I (SUR? : NO) → [RT, CT]
Stage II				
Rules		Sup.	Conf.	Clinical guidelines
II.3	IIB → [SUR]	4.03 %	73.33 %	I (SUR? : YES) → [CT, SUR]
II.4	IIA → [SUR]	1.47 %	88.89 %	I (SUR? : NO) → [RT, CT]
Stage III				
Rules		Sup.	Conf.	Clinical guidelines
II.5	IIIA → [CT]	8.06 %	61.97 %	III (RES? : YES) → [CT]
II.6	IIIB → [CT]	7.51 %	71.93 %	IIIA (RES? : POT) → [CT, SUR]
II.7	IIIA → [SUR]	3.85 %	29.58 %	III (RES? : POT) → [conc(CT+RT), SUR]
II.8	IIIC → [CT]	3.11 %	94.44 %	III (RES? : NO) → [conc(CT+RT), DRUGS]
				III (RES? : NO) → [seq(CT+RT)]
Stage IV				
Rules		Sup.	Conf.	Clinical guidelines
II.9	IV → [CT]	18.13 %	80.49 %	IV (MUT? : YES) → [DRUGS]
II.10	IVB → [CT]	10.81 %	54.63 %	IV (MUT? : YES) → [conc(DRUGS+CT)]
II.11	IVA → [CT]	8.24 %	70.31 %	IV (MUT? : YES) → [seq(DRUGS+CT)]
II.12	IVB → [RT]	6.59 %	49.32 %	IV (MUT? : NO) → [conc(DRUGS+CT)]
II.13	IV → [RT]	3.30 %	24.66 %	IV (MUT? : NO) → [conc(CT+IMM)]
II.14	IVB → [conc(CT+RT)]	1.47 %	47.06 %	IV (MUT? : NO) → [IMM]
				IV (OLIG? : YES) → [RT]
				IV (MET? : YES) → [RT]
				IV (PAL? : YES) → [RT]

and III.5), CT_{Intrav&Oral} (rules III.1 and III.9). It should be noted that treatments types (i.e. CT and RT) with subtype *Null*, means that the subtype was missing in the dataset.

On the other hand, association rules also reveal that radiotherapy (RT) has been extensively used as a first treatment for cancer stages IV, IVA and IVB (rules: III.6, III.10, III.12, III.14, III.16, III.18). Even for some cases, CT is prescribed as first treatment but with the intention to be concurrent with RT (rules III.19 and III.19). According to clinical guidelines, radical RT is prescribed for patients with oligometastatic non-small cell lung cancer. In addition, palliative RT is prescribed as primary treatment for patients with metastases or locally advanced tumors that are not candidates to be treated with curative therapies. Also, in patients with comorbidities, advanced age, or non-operable tumors.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have performed an Apriori analysis of a dataset containing treatments prescriptions for lung cancer patients. As a result of the analysis, association rules are obtained showing treatments applied depending on the cancer stage. Additionally, association rules are compared with clinical guidelines in order to find agreements and deviations.

The comparison reveals that for stages IA and IB, surgery is primarily applied in agreement with clinical recommendations, since neoadjuvant CT before surgery is optional depending on tumor characteristics. For stage III, treatment patterns found mostly match with clinical guidelines, where chemotherapy and surgery are prescribed as first treatment. Regarding stage

IV, agreement with clinical guidelines is also found since radiotherapy, targeted oral therapy, immunotherapy and intravenous and oral chemotherapy are prescribed as initial treatments.

Results presented in this paper are a preliminary study of treatment patterns found in lung cancer patients. Nevertheless, we plan to extend this study by including extra patient and cancer data from the dataset in order to find prescription patterns depending on inter and inpatients' variability of response to the possible treatments. Additionally, we plan to include treatment outcome information in order to evaluate treatment prescriptions that are aligned or not with respect to clinical guidelines.

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TABLE III
SPECIFIC ASSOCIATION RULES AND CLINICAL GUIDELINES RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STAGE IV

Stage IV				
Rules	Sup.	Conf.	Clinical guidelines	
III.1	IV → [CT _{Intrav&Oral}]	3.85 %	42.00 %	IV (MUT? : YES) → [DRUGS] IV (MUT? : YES) → [conc(DRUGS+CT _{Intrav})] IV (MUT? : YES) → [seq(DRUGS+CT _{Intrav})] IV (MUT? : NO) → [conc(CT _{Intrav&Oral} +CT _{Intrav})] IV (MUT? : NO) → [conc(CT _{Intrav} +IMM)] IV (MUT? : NO) → [IMM] IV (OLIG? : YES) → [RT _{Radical}] IV (MET? : YES) → [RT _{Pallia}] IV (PAL? : YES) → [RT _{Pallia}]
III.2	IV → [CT _{Null}]	3.30 %	30.00 %	
III.3	IV → [CT _{Intrav.}]	3.30 %	21.18 %	
III.4	IVB → [CT _{Intrav.}]	3.30 %	21.18 %	
III.5	IVA → [CT _{Intrav.}]	2.93 %	25.00 %	
III.6	IVB → [RT _{Null}]	2.56 %	40.00 %	
III.7	IV → [CT _{Adj}]	2.38 %	35.14 %	
III.8	IVB → [CT _{Neoadj}]	1.83 %	23.81 %	
III.9	IVB → [CT _{Intrav&Oral}]	1.83 %	20.00 %	
III.10	IVB → [RT _{Radical}]	1.65 %	64.29 %	
III.11	IV → [CT _{CT-RTSeq}]	1.65 %	37.50 %	
III.12	IV → [RT _{Null}]	1.65 %	25.71 %	
III.13	IV → [CT _{Neoadj}]	1.65 %	21.43 %	
III.14	IVB → [RT _{Pallia}]	1.47 %	50.00 %	
III.15	IV → [CT _{Drugs}]	0.92 %	35.71 %	
III.16	IV → [RT _{Pallia}]	0.92 %	31.25 %	
III.17	IVB → [CT _{Drugs}]	0.73 %	28.57 %	
III.18	IVB → [RT _{Adj}]	0.55 %	75.00 %	
III.19	IV → [CT _{CT-RTC onc}]	0.55 %	42.86 %	
III.20	IVA → [CT _{CT-RTC onc}]	0.55 %	42.86 %	

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